

MEDIATING ROLE OF JOB SATISFACTION IN THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MEANING OF WORK AND INTENTION TO LEAVE

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Abstract

Quality human resources are needed to face challenges in the world of work. The quality of human resources can be improved through non-formal education which ultimately gives birth to more job training institutions (LPK). One measure of LPK's success in producing quality human resources is the presence of competent instructors, but some of these instructors actually have the desire to stop working. Based on this, this research aims to explain the influence of meaning of work and job satisfaction on intention to leave and explain the influence of meaning of work on job satisfaction. In addition, this research also explains the role of job satisfaction as a mediator in the influence of the meaning of work on intention to leave. This research is quantitative research with data collection methods through questionnaires. The questionnaire was distributed to 176 instructors at LPK Denpasar city who were then analyzed using partial least squares (PLS). The research results show that the meaning of work and job satisfaction have a significant effect on intention to leave. Meaning of work also has a significant effect on job satisfaction. Job satisfaction can act as a mediator in the influence of the meaning of work on intention to leave.

Keywords: Meaning of Work, Job Satisfaction, Intention to Leave.

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a crucial role in developing quality human resources (Elis & Santika, 2018). Non-formal education through Job Training Institutes (LPK) serves as a platform to equip individuals with the specialized skills, knowledge, and attitudes needed in the industrial sector (Ramoo et al., 2013). The demand for improved living standards through non-formal education has spurred the establishment of more LPKs. In Denpasar City, Bali, the development of LPKs has been notably rapid, with 54 institutions currently operational, 25 of which focus on the hospitality sector (Denpasar City Manpower Office, 2023). These LPKs prepare potential workers to meet industry needs. The success of LPKs largely depends on their instructors, whose competence reflects the quality of the human resources produced (Ihwanudin, 2016). However, challenges arise as each instructor has unique abilities and career orientations.

Research indicates that not all instructors are fully prepared for institutional demands. A number of senior instructors struggle with technological advancements, especially the use of internal digital systems and the tools required to carry out training activities. This lack of familiarity can increase the intention of instructors to leave the institution, particularly if they feel unable to meet its evolving demands. Interviews with four instructors revealed that, despite their experience in the hospitality industry, they faced difficulties when transitioning to the role of an instructor due to the requirement to use technology in creating teaching materials and videos. Additionally, younger instructors expressed a desire to further their education or pursue career advancement, which contributes to their intention to leave.

Intention to leave has become a significant issue in many organizations, driven by various factors (Alias et al., 2018). One critical factor influencing an individual's desire to leave is the meaning of work (Scroggins, 2008; Arnoux-Nicolas et al., 2016; Fouché et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2019; Guerci et al., 2019; Haaland et al., 2020). The meaning of work refers to a person's broad perspective regarding the significance of their work (Steger, 2016). Job satisfaction also plays a crucial role in an employee's decision to remain in an organization (Ramoo et al., 2013; Sabanciogullari & Dogan, 2015; Arnup & Bowles, 2016; Amunkete & Rothmann, 2015; Gebregziabher et al., 2020).

Although numerous studies have been conducted on the intention to leave, research on this phenomenon among non-formal education instructors remains scarce. This study focuses on Job Training Institutes (LPKs) in the hospitality sector and aims to explore the mediation and moderation effects of job satisfaction. Furthermore, this research introduces the concept of Karma Yoga as a novel dimension in the meaning of work variable, reflecting local wisdom in work-related contexts (Foster et al., 2021; Anggraeni, 2015).

Based on the aforementioned points, this research aims to explain the influence of the meaning of work and job satisfaction on the intention to leave, as well as the mediating role of job satisfaction in this relationship. Given the crucial role of LPK instructors in developing superior human resources for Bali's tourism industry, addressing the phenomenon of intention to leave is of paramount importance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Intention to leave refers to an employee's desire to leave an organization (Aziz & Ramli, 2010). According to Kitapci et al. (2005), intention to leave is the desire or intention that arises in an individual to depart from an organization. This intention can be linked to the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which predicts individual behaviors based on intentions. TPB has been widely applied in social psychology to predict and explain behaviors and actions (Kan & Fabrigar, 2017; Fukukawa, 2002; Ryu et al., 2003).

This research is a development of research conducted by (Scroggins, 2008), that meaning of It is very important to improve work to reduce feelings of wanting to leave a job or organization. The mediating variable is job satisfaction was also added in this research. According to (Weiss, 2002), jobs Satisfaction is a positive assessment and view of someone's working conditions. Furthermore (Weiss, 2002), considers job satisfaction as a person's awareness of whether or not they like the work they do.

When workers consider work they very meaningful, then in a way no direct they develop a deep sense of ownership to work they are and they are not will leave work the without the right solution or give up on the organization although face difficulty nor obstacles (Pradhan and Jena, 2017). Study results literature from study previous indicated that there is influence negative and significant between meaning of work with intention to leave, so the more tall level meaning of work someone, then the more low desire somebody For leave organization or work (Pradhan and Jena, 2017; Arnoux - Nicolas et al., 2016; Sun et al., 2019; Guerci, et al. 2019; Fouché et al., 2017).

Meaningful work can cause change attitude somebody because attitude the reflect system trust about his job, in other words that work somebody that valuable and useful in the future can cause various attitude positive one of them is satisfaction work. Someone who has level high job satisfaction is greatly influenced by a high meaning of work, the caused by meaning work that has role as dimensions

psychological somebody For reach satisfaction work in his job (Jordan et al., 2017; Fairlie, 2011; Golparvar & Abedini, 2014; Humphrey et al., 2007; Keleş & Fındıklı , 2016; Allan et al., 2018; Ribeiro & Marra, 2021).

Job satisfaction not only does it encourage individuals to behave positively such as being more productive, disciplined, obedient, innovative, helpful but can also control negative behavior such as corruption, theft, vandalism and leaving the company (Greenidge et al., 2014). There is a negative influence and significant between jobs satisfaction with intention to leave, where research empirical previous mention that someone who has level low job satisfaction will own level high intention to leave (Ramoo et al., 2013; Sabanciogullari & Dogan, 2015; Arnup & Bowles, 2016; Amunkete & Rothmann, 2015; Gebregziabher et al., 2020).

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

Previous research shows that there is a direct influence between meaning of work with jobs satisfaction. This is in accordance with research empirical research conducted by (Keleş & Fındıklı , 2016; Jordan et al., 2017; Fairlie, 2011; Golparvar & Abedini, 2014) jobs satisfaction also has a strong effect on intention to leave (Peng et al., 2016). These results are supported by research conducted by (Sabanciogullari & Dogan, 2015; Arnup & Bowles, 2016) which explains that there is a positive and significant influence between job satisfaction with intention to leave. So, the research explains that job satisfaction mediates the influence of meaning of work on intention to leave.

Based on review literature about the variables meaning of work, job satisfaction, and intention to leave can be arranged framework conceptual as in Figure 1. Hypothesis study based on figure 1 skeleton conceptual above can arranged as following: H1: Meaning of work has a negative and significant effect on intention to leave. H2: Meaning of work has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. H3: Job s atisfaction has a negative and significant effect on intention to leave. H4: Job satisfaction mediating the influence of meaning of work towards p intention to leave

METHOD

This research uses a quantitative approach based on the philosophy of positivism, namely pointing out the influence between the variables meaning of work, job satisfaction, and intention to leave. The measurement indicators for each research variable are explained in Table 1.

Table 1. Variable indicators

Variable	Indicator	Source
Intention to leave (Y2)	(1) Thinking of quitting (2) Intention to search for alternatives (3) Intention to quit	(Skelton et al., 2020; Srisakun, 2022; Annell et al., 2022)
Job satisfaction (Y1)	(1) Job itself (2) Supervision (3) Rewards (pay) (4) Promotion (5) Co-workers	(Natalia et al., 2020; Sari et al., 2019)
Meaning of Work (X1)	(1) Work centrality (2) Social norms (3) Valued work outcomes (4) Importance of work goals (5) Work role identification (6) Karma yoga	(Bianchi, 2018; Anggraeni 2015)

Table 2. Respondent demographics

Characteristics	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	≤ 25 years	10	5.68 %
	26-30 yrs	53	30.11 %
	31-35 yrs	48	27.27 %
	36-40 yrs	12	6.82 %
	41-45 yrs	23	13.07 %
	46-50 years old	10	5.68 %
	≥ 50 years old	20	11.36 %
last education	≤ SMA/SMK	19	10.80 %
	Diploma	53	30.11 %
	S1	72	40.91 %
	S2	32	18.18 %
	Type sex	Man	98
	Woman	78	44.32 %
Total		176	100%

This research was conducted in the LPK field hotels in Denpasar City whose operational permits are still active until January 2023. The research respondents were LPK instructors totaling 176 people with the sampling technique used in this research being sample bored, because amount instructor of each relative LPK small, so amount sample the same with amount its population that is as many as 176 people. Data collection was carried out using a survey method through questionnaires and so on processed using partial analysis least square (PLS).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Respondent study A total of 176 instructors came from from the Training Institute Work (LPK) in the city of Denpasar, described in table 2. Analysis results descriptive respondents in Table 2 show that part big instructor who became samples

in research This 26 years old up to 30 years as many as 53 people (30.11%) of the total respondents totaling 176 people. From education final respondents majority undergraduate (S1) as many as 72 people (40.91%) of the total respondents totaling 176 people. Then reviewed from type genitals, some big is manifold sex man as many as 98 people (55.68%).

Evaluation of the measurement model (outer model) is necessary done moreover formerly before done structural model evaluation. Evaluation of measurement models consists from a number of thing, that is convergent validity, discriminant validity and composite reliability. Testing convergent validity uses the outer loading value is obtained that all items on the variable meaning of work (X1), job satisfaction (Y1), and intention to leave (Y2) are valid, because mark outer loading overall item range between 0.552 – 0.801 more of 0.5. That matter show that measurement model has own good convergent validity.

Then testing discriminant validity uses Fornell-Larcker Criterion shows that mark root square of the latent construct AVE consisting of from meaning of work (X1), job satisfaction (Y1), and intention to leave (Y2) respectively are 0.716, 0.745, and 0.751 greater than the correlation value between one construct and another construct , so that in a way whole deep latent construct study This Enough unique and capable catch the phenomenon being measured.

Testing reliability use composite reliability is obtained that whole variable research consisting from each has meaning of work (X1), job satisfaction (Y1), and intention to leave (Y2). mark composite reliability of 0.862, 0.862, and 0.795 more of 0.7, so all over construct has reliable.

After the measurement model has been valid and reliable, then furthermore can done evaluation on structural models. Goodness of fit of the structural model (inner model) was tested use value, R- square and Q- square for measure how much good mark observation generated by models and estimates the parameters. R- square value on the path influence meaning of work (X1) against job satisfaction (Y1) is 0.072 which means that meaning of work capable explain job satisfaction was 7.2 percent, meanwhile the rest amounting to 92.8 percent explained by other variables that are not researched. R- square value in the structural model this classified weak. Then R- square value on the path influence meaning of work (X1) and job satisfaction (Y1) towards intention to leave (Y2) is 0.146 which is significant that meaning of work and job satisfaction able explain intention to leave was 12.9 percent, while the rest amounting to 87.1 percent explained by other variables that are not researched. R- square value in the structural model this classified weak. Whereas Q- square value is 0.192, value the has more from 0, so model has own predictive relevance. Q- square value is in the range 0.02 – 0.35, so classified as a moderate model.

After testing model accuracy is performed, then can done testing hypothesis as listed in Table 3. Table 3 shows hypothesis test results research, meaning of work and job satisfaction have an influence significant to intention to leave, because mark t- statistics > 1.96 and pvalues < 0.05, so H1 and H3 can be accepted. So case with The meaning of work also has an influence significant to intention to leave via mediation job satisfaction, so H4 can accepted. Besides that the meaning of work also has an influence significant to job satisfaction, so H2 can be accepted. The path analysis model is shown in Figure 2.

Table 3. Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis	Path of Influence	Original Sample	t-statistics	P values	Information
H1	Meaning of Work (X1) -> Intention to Leave (Y2)	-0,267	5,095	0,000	Significant (support)
H2	Meaning of Work (X1) -> Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0,269	3,641	0.0 00	Significant (support)
H3	Jobs Satisfaction (Y1) -> Intention to Leave (Y2)	-0 .179	3,292	0.00 1	Significant (support)
H4	Meaning of Work (X1) -> Job Satisfaction (Y1) -> Intention to Leave (Y2)	-0.0 48	2, 449	0.0 15	Significant (support)

Figure 2. Formed path analysis model

Discussion

Testing of hypothesis 1 (H1) shows that meaning of work (X1) has a negative and significant effect on intention to leave (Y2). That matter caused Because meaning of work reviewed from dimensions work centrality, valued work outcomes and karma yoga, shows that the LPK instructors in the field Hoteliers in Denpasar understand how important and valuable their job persevere moment this, as well in working is also practicing Karma Yoga values in everyday life, so although income received felt not enough they still endure for continue career as instructor at each LPK. So that matter the make dimensions work of centrality, valued work outcomes, and karma yoga from variable Meaning of work as factor affecting low desire instructor for leaving LPK where it is Work moment this. Research result This support results research previously revealed that influence negative and significant between meaning of work with intention to leave identify that the more tall level meaning of work someone, then the more low desire somebody For leave organization or work (Pradhan & Jena, 2017; Arnoux-Nicolas et al., 2016; Sun et al., 2019; Guerri et al., 2019; Fouché et al., 2017). When workers consider work they very meaningful, then in a way No direct they develop a deep sense of ownership to work they are and they are not will leave work the without the right solution or give up on the organization although face difficulty nor barriers (Pradhan & Jena, 2017).

The results of testing hypothesis 2 (H2) are meaning of work (X1) has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction (Y1) produces a positive path coefficient. That

matter caused because meaning of work reviewed from dimensions work centrality, valued work outcomes, and karma yoga show that the LPK instructors in the field Hoteliers in Denpasar understand how important and valuable their job persevere moment this , as well in working is also practicing Karma Yoga values in everyday life, so although income received felt not enough they still endure for continue career as instructors at each LPK. So that matter the make dimensions work of centrality, valued work outcomes and karma yoga from variable Meaning of work as factor affecting increased job satisfaction field LPK instructor Hotels in Denpasar. Research result this support results research previously mentioned that someone who has level High job satisfaction is greatly influenced by high meaning of work the caused by meaning work that has role as dimensions psychological somebody for reach satisfaction work in his job (Jordan et al., 2017; Fairlie, 2011; Golparvar & Abedini, 2014; Humphrey et al., 2007; Keleş & Fındıklı , 2016; Allan et al., 2018; Ribeiro & Marra, 2021). Meaning of work own very important role for life someone who can influence all aspect life somebody including satisfaction it works (Rosso et al., 2010). Studies conducted (Allan et al., 2018) found that meaningful work can cause change attitude somebody Because attitude the reflect system trust about his job, in other words that work somebody that valuable and useful in the future can cause various attitude positive one of them is satisfaction work.

Test result to hypothesis 3 (H3) namely job satisfaction (Y1) has an effect negative and significant to intention to leave (Y2) results coefficient track marked negative. That matter caused Because job satisfaction reviewed from dimensions type work (Job itself) and relationships with colleague work (co-workers) show that field LPK instructor Hospitality in Denpasar stated his satisfaction related chance available promotions moment this because opportunity this can obtained from internal LPK, work as instructor involved moment this has according to what is desired and the instructor also conveys it satisfied during cooperate with colleagues fellow instructor. So that matter the make dimensions promotion, job itself, and c o-workers from variable job satisfaction as factor affecting low desire instructor for leaving LPK where it is work moment this. Research result this support results research previously revealed that there is a negative influence and significant between jobs satisfaction with intention to leave, where research empirical previous mention that someone who has level low job satisfaction will own level high intention to leave (Ramoo et al., 2013); Sabanciogullari & Dogan, 2015; Arnup & Bowles, 2016; Amunkete & Rothmann, 2015; Kusin , Al Gaffrie Mil., Tajuddin, Dewi ., Ambad , Sylvia, 2021; Kusin , Al Gaffrie Mil., Tajuddin, Dewi., Ambad, Sylvia, 2021; Kusin, Al Gaffrie Mil., Tajuddin, Dewi., Ambad, Sylvia, 2021; Gebregziabher et al., 2020). Job satisfaction not only does it encourage individuals to behave positively such as being more productive, disciplined, obedient, innovative, helpful but can also control negative behavior such as corruption, theft, vandalism and leaving the company (Greenidge et al., 2014). Basically, job satisfaction influenced by capacity psychological someone who can develop in a way positive nor negative. If someone own capacity positive psychology , then level owned job satisfaction will high, so will difficult for somebody For leave his job (Amunkete & Rothmann, 2015) .

Test result to hypothesis 4 (H4) namely job satisfaction (Y1) mediates the effect of meaning of work (X1) on intention to leave (Y2), results coefficient track marked negative. That matter give information, hints, and options for institution in effort decline intention to leave instructor at the training Institute Work field Denpasar Bali hotels. Option First is the Institution can only focuses on level meaning of work carried out

institution in frame lower Intention to leave instructors. Option secondly, institutions can also consider aspect job satisfaction, in meaning level meaning of work instructor can focused moreover formerly in increase job satisfaction, which is next matter the will with itself impact on decline Intention to leave instructors. Research result this support a number of study the previous one concluded that job satisfaction can mediating the influence of meaning of work on intention to leave (Arnoux-Nicolas et al., 2016; Keleş & Fındıklı, 2016; Sun et al., 2019; Guerçi et al., 2019; Fouché et al., 2017). Meaning of work own very important role for life someone who can influence all aspect life somebody including satisfaction it works (Rosso et al., 2010). Intention to leave occurs when someone does not feel satisfied with the work they are doing, so that someone consciously looks for other job alternatives (Martin & Roodt, 2008).

CONCLUSION

His height level intention to leave at LPK Denpasar city requires efforts special for minimize it. A number of possible factors lower level intention to leave instructor at LPK Denpasar city is meaning of work and job satisfaction. Satisfaction Work instructor can improved through meaning of work. Influence meaning of work towards intention to leave will the more strong if supported by job satisfaction. Some possible suggestions given to field LPK instructors hotels in the city of Denpasar Bali are always improved through work role identification that explains about the extent to which LPK instructors in the hospitality sector in Denpasar evaluate and identify work from various roles and functions as an instructof. Possible efforts carried out by LPK include : 1) carrying out evaluation performance instructor; 2) give chance learning and development through training competence specifically in matter use technology in the teaching process; 3) hold socialization with give motivation that meaning1Work a instructor Work with sincere be sincere without think about rewards with put forward moral values, values devotion, value education, values Yadnya, value professionalism and value Love love; 4) give burden work that doesn't too burdensome for instructors ; 5) do evaluation about policy stipulated salary For instructor; 6) give opportunity for instructors for ask if not yet understand instruction superior as well as give input, suggestions and criticism if felt method delivery direction by superiors not yet can understandable; 7) improve satisfaction work through giving rewards, bonuses, etc award for instructor who has performance good work.

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